

Optimising the life cycle costs in defence industry

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Abstract: The focus of this study is to highlight the importance of managing Life Cycle Costs (LCC) in defence acquisition and contracting. Acquisition & contracting is an important yet under explored area especially in the public sector domain. In public sector acquisitions where the amount and effort involved in executing complete process of a single high-end equipment is so high, it makes it an imperative area to be explored in detail. Furthermore, there is a dire need to find out a suitable framework which allows the organisation to optimise the life cycle cost in these acquisitions. To achieve this aim, this paper has provided a ground for future research direction in this area. Firstly, life cycle cost factors have been summarised. Secondly, research themes have been proposed based on the literature. Third, specific research questions have been proposed. Fourth, research methodology has also been suggested for the future research. In conclusion, this paper summarises the LCC factors, research issues & themes, possible future research directions in optimising the life cycle cost in defence acquisitions.

Keywords: Life Cycle Cost, Lean, Agile, Resilient, Sustainable, Acquisition, Contracting, Defence Industry

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Introduction

Organisations worldwide are involved in multiple purchasing activities irrespective of the nature of business they are involved in. This is usually done by building and maintaining thorough relationships both upstream and downstream the Supply Chains. These purchases start from procuring smallest raw materials required for production; like small screws, and further raises to a level where complete systems and equipment are purchased on a larger scale. On a smaller scale, purchasing and procurement departments of organisations have been handling these affairs efficiently. However, when we talk about expensive and complex systems, its purchasing requires more formal and structured procedures (Serman, 1994). This led to the evolution of a separate discipline of acquisition and contract management (McIlvaine, 2000). Acquisition and contracting as a proper focus have been actively used in major government and defense related acquisitions due to the sensitive nature of these systems (Callender and Matthews, 2000). Acquiring the right system at the right time is the most important factor in high end acquisitions (Feickert, 2006). Lengthy acquisition processes in large end equipment or systems may directly translate to a poor and hampered capability of any organization. Moreover, unexpected high cost of concept phase of these purchases and then the execution phase of these

projects may create budget hindrances for the organisations as well (Loudin, 2010). Therefore, managing the complete acquisition program of high-end systems in the limited budget is an important and challenging task.

This paper attempts to highlight the need of understanding the complete life cycle cost; from cradle to grave; for the acquisitions of high-end system and equipment purchases. When we talk about high end systems, these include acquiring high end Information technology software, acquiring complex adaptive systems like defense or military stores. Hence for the purpose of discussion, the stores, equipment, and systems will be referred as high-end system acquisitions in this study. This study attempts to highlight the important of managing and measuring life cycle costs in defense acquisitions. Furthermore, this paper aims to suggest future research directions in finding out suitable ways of measuring the life cycle costs of different acquisitions. Keeping in view the importance of this area, it is considered an provocative and important idea to find out a suitable framework of optimising the life cycle cost in high end acquisitions.

Literature Review

To maintain a military force that is always ready to face any uncertain situation in today's dynamically changing world is inevitable. This is not possible without the acquisition and procurement of new and technologically advanced equipment, stores and systems which are a major expense for any nation. Study of the literature reveals that Defense Acquisition is a comprehensive process that helps to translate the user requirements into products, services and information required to satisfy needs (Allen, 2008). It is a process that deals with investing the budget in the systems, stores, products, technologies, and programs necessary to achieve the strategic intent of any nation's security policy in building its armed forces (Schwartz, 2010). One of the most important aspects in the term of defense acquisition is its comprehensiveness. Defense acquisition does not only mean to acquire any system, yet it deals with complete life cycle management of the equipment starting from conception, design, planning, contracting, acquisition, installation, usage, maintenance, and disposal (Schindler, 2010). Additionally, Erridge and McIlroy (2002) argue that public procurement processes are strongly tied to Supply Chain strategies. Therefore, the significance of effective management of these acquisitions becomes very extremely important.

Although the comprehensive concept of defense acquisition has evolved in the recent years, but its foundations are not new. The history of defense acquisition dates to ancient times. Starting from blacksmithing to shipbuilding and to the increasingly complex weapon systems of in the 21st century, its importance has increased over the period (Jones, 1999). Defense Acquisition is therefore a process that is critical to the survival of military organizations. There is a dire need that defense acquisition be given priority in funding to improve quality and be recognized as the important element in enhancing organisations capabilities (Kadish et. al., 2006). The defense industry worldwide is shifting its focus by bringing radical changes in acquisition processes due to Just in-Time inventory practices, widespread supply-chain integration, and digitization (Davidow & Malone, 1992), electronic markets (Pomazalová & Korecki, 2011), mass customization (Pine et al., 1993) and other contemporary business practices. In other words, being Lean is a way saving cost but being responsive (Agile) is the demand of the time. Hence, procurement focus has shifted away from short-term to long term strategic partnerships. Although cost is still vitally important, it is no longer necessarily more so than capability, quality, reliability, and trustworthiness. In today's era of disruptive competition (D'Aveni, 1994), expanding global operations and exploding information; organisations realize that environment is changing dynamically and demands for a structured change.

Among various other factors, one of the most important factors in defense acquisitions is cost. Study of the literature reveals that cost of purchasing or manufacturing is only a small part of the overall cost of the purchase (Kaplan, 1992).

In addition to the cost of purchasing, there are running costs, maintenance costs, execution costs and disposal costs. Therefore, the idea of Life Cycle Cost management has been coined to encompass all relevant costs. Life Cycle Cost (LCC) is referred as the cost involved in the acquisition program from cradle to grave. Hence it involves the investment costs, R & D costs, operating costs, support costs, disposal costs and maintenance costs over the life cycle of equipment or system (Gluch & Baumann, 2004). In other words, it includes all the direct and indirect costs over the life cycle of the product. Due to the peculiar nature of the defense products, the importance of life cycle costs has increased manifold. In case of defense acquisitions, procuring the lowest cost item is not always the solution. Rather, a product is procured on the concept of lifelong ownership. This concept has evolved over the time and its importance has increased manifold. The stores, equipment and systems in defense acquisitions need to be acquired on the basis of their lifetime usability, supportability and disposal (Sauser et al., 2009). Studies have found that in calculating the life cycle cost of equipment the cost is on the higher side, but in the longer run the average costs are much less (Sherif & Kolarik, 1981). Therefore, it's very important that comprehensive and systematic life cycle cost analysis be carried out to establish, control and reduce the costs. This study has carried out extensive review of literature to find out the most important determinants or factors of life cycle cost measurement. Summary of the important factors involved in Life Cycle Cost analysis are presented in figure 1 (Woodward, 1997; Sauser et al., 2009; Dhillon, 2013 and Asiedu, 1998):

Life Cycle Cost Factors	Taking right design trade off decisions
	Selecting correct design options
	Determine cost drivers
	Correct source selections
	Strict program control
	Contractor incentives
	Technology applications
	Training needs analysis
	Forecast of future budget

Fig. 1: Life Cycle Cost Factors

With the introduction of the concept of product quality by (Garvin, 1988), the defense industry has discovered that quality represents a critical performance factor, and that emphasizing quality can save cost and reduce cycle time. Drucker (1998) claims product innovations may take as long as 50 years to reach and affect the market. In light of the time and quality factors, now there is a dire need that suitable way be carved out between cost vs quality and cost vs time. According to Garvin (1987), there are eight dimensions of quality. In case of defense acquisitions, there is no option of comprising on quality. Therefore, it's important to find out a suitable match between quality with budget. Similarly, the changing security dynamics of the world require cycle times to be reduced as well. However, it's not possible at the expense of higher costs. So, the need of the time is to find out the right balance between acquisition cycle times – vs costs vs increased flexibility and reduced delays in delivering the equipment and systems.

Contribution And Future Research Directions

This paper highlighted the importance of life cycle cost management in the defense acquisitions and contracting. It also discussed the relationship between Cost & quality in the acquisition of defense related stores. Besides, understanding the importance of LCC with cost and quality, there is a dire need that a proper framework be established which may help the optimize the life cycle costs. Therefore, this paper attempts to present future research opportunities in the field of optimising the life cycle cost in defence acquisitions. It is to highlight that extensive research in this domain has been conducted in the manufacturing sector, especially in the automotive industry, whereas less work has been conducted in the public sector (Sharma et al., 2021). It has been observed in the literature that most research in this area is focused either on the public sector services with less focus on the public sector systems and equipment acquisitions. Based on the discussions in this paper, the following future research directions are suggested to be pursued:

1. What are the important elements of defence acquisitions?
2. What, if any, are the synergies and divergences among the elements of defence acquisition paradigms?
3. How do the elements of defence acquisition affect each another?
4. What is life cycle management in public procurement programs?
5. What are the elements of Life Cycle management?
6. How is life cycle cost management related to the acquisition and contracting?
7. How do the acquisition practices sequentially impact all the life cycle stages of a product?
8. How do the acquisition practices sequentially and simultaneously affect the defence sector?
9. What is the relationship between acquisitioning and Supply Chain strategies?
10. What are the elements of Life cycle cost management?
11. What is the relationship between Life cycle cost management and acquisition & contracting?
12. Which factors of Life cycle cost management are related to defence acquisitions?
13. How quality is related to Life cycle cost management?
14. How is life cycle time related to Life cycle cost management?
15. How be life cycle costs be optimised in defence acquisitions?
16. What is the nature of relationship between cycle time, product quality and life cycle cost in defence acquisitions?
17. Is the integration of the life cycle time and quality for achieving the maximum potential of optimising life cycle costs?
18. What is the impact of the combinations of these practices (LARGS) on the conventional performance matrix?
19. What is the impact of using life cycle cost model on the dynamic capabilities (structural and unstructured) of organisations?
20. Are there any trade-off between focusing on cycle time, quality and new emerging technological interventions (Industry 4.0) ?
21. Can a framework for optimising the life cycle costs be proposed in acquisitions and contracting? If yes, then, what are the most crucial factors of optimised life cycle cost framework?
22. How the implementation of Life cycle cost practices impact with each other at the organisational level and an end-to-end supply chain?
23. What is the nature of relationship between Optimising the life cycle cost (LCC) and the following Supply Chain Management Approaches:
 - a. Optimising LCC and Lean approach

- b. Optimising LCC and Agile approach
- c. Optimising LCC and Resilient approach
- d. Optimising LCC and Sustainable approach

Research Questions

Based on the discussion above, this study further presents some research questions which may be considered for exploring the topic further.

Research Question 1:

How can life cycle costs be effectively measured and evaluated?

Sub Questions:

- What all factors should be included in measuring the Life Cycle Cost (LCC) of defense acquisitions?
- Which method is most effective in measuring the LCC in defense acquisitions?

Research Question 2:

How to calculate the impact of life cycle cost on the cycle time and quality of defense acquisition?

Sub Questions:

- What is the impact of reducing life cycle cost on the cycle time?
- What is the impact of reducing life cycle cost on the product quality?

Research Question 3:

How can the life cycle cost be modeled to determine the optimal level of efficiency in defense acquisitions?

Sub Questions:

- Which models of life cycle cost management of defense acquisitions are currently used?
- Which is the most suitable model for life cycle cost management of defense acquisitions to optimize the efficiency?

Research Methodology

Based on the study of literature and proposed research directions, future research may adopt a mixed research methodology consisting of both qualitative and quantitative techniques for data analysis. Due to the nature of the topic and limitations of the data availability, combination of two technique may provide more comprehensive results. This methodology has been previously tested by Jick (1979) in his research. In studies where policy, public decision making and social aspects are involved, the combination of interpretivist and positivist approaches can provide both the causal 'How' and the causal 'What' answers; something which these approaches cannot provide alone (Lin, 1998).

With respect to the positivist aspect, a quantitative framework is considered suitable when addressing problems of organizational and policy nature (Spender, 1996). This may require understanding and quantifying monetary savings for each incremental increase or decrease in cycle-time. Therefore, data may be collected, and regression analysis be conducted to establish the impact between independent and dependent variables. The results will help to understand the implications in triggering the cost vs quality and cost vs cycle time. This study proposes following conceptual framework based on the study of literature:

Figure 2 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis 1

H1 0 Reducing life cycle cost will not increase the life cycle time.

H1 A Reducing life cycle cost will increase the life cycle time

Hypothesis 2

H2 0 Reducing life cycle cost will not affect the product quality.

H2 A Reducing life cycle cost will affect the product quality.

From the interpretivist perspective, addition of qualitative aspects can bring in the perspectival view of the study which may not be obvious in quantitative analysis (Fielding and Schreier, 2001). In this regard, semi structured interviews are suggested to undertake the study. (Borzillo and Deschaux, 2020) carried secondary analysis of the studies conducted in the defence sector and found it useful. Semi structured interviews can bring in some themes which may bring in some underlying factors not visible in the quantitative analysis. This will help to understand the essence of optimization of life cycle costs in defence acquisitions.

Significance of The Future Research

Future research in this domain will assist all the stakeholders involved in procurement, provisioning, and acquisition of defense stores. This will include the users, technical advisors, and logistic managers. By having a better understanding of the life cycle cost of the defense acquisitions, future projects will have a better planning, improved budgeting, and enhanced supervision. Ultimately this will help in savings costs and efficiency gains, particularly in through-life maintenance and progressive upgrades.

Limitations of This Study

One of the main limitations of this work is, its highly descriptive and theoretical. However, it helps to identify future research directions and possible questions to be explored in this area. This study is a source of reflection for the scholars aiming to address the issues in this domain. Another future limitation which may arise, is the limited availability of data for analysis. Due to the sensitive nature of equipment involved in the defense acquisitions, the data is not openly available. Therefore, the analysis will mainly rely on the available literature on the subject and the available open sources like SIPRI (Fontanel, 2022). However, studies can be conducted internally in organisations where results may not be shown publicly.

Conclusion

Study of the literature reveals that some pioneering work in this area was undertaken by the departments of defence of some countries. However, work in this area was largely motivated by funded programs. Moreover, there are there are limited studies and literature which proposes a well worked framework or model to be followed in this area. Therefore, the need of the time is to focus on proposing a framework for defence acquisitions keeping in view the life cycle cost and life cycle management of systems. All stakeholders in acquisition or project management should collaborate in gaining new knowledge and recognize the possibilities of developing incommensurable paradigms. This research helps to identify and set the direction for future researchers to follow and explore new dimensions.

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